

Synthesis and Anti-inflammatory Activity of a Few 5-(Indan-1'-yl)methyltetrazoles

A. ROY, J. K. GUPTA and S. C. LAHIRI*

Department of Pharmacy, Jadavpur University, Calcutta-700 082

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In an attempt to develop relatively less toxic and more potent anti-inflammatory agents than the presently available ones, a few 5-(indan-1'-yl)methyltetrazoles have been synthesised and subjected to anti-inflammatory screening. Two of them showed anti-inflammatory potency close to that of phenylbutazone in both acute (carrageenin-induced edema) and chronic (adjuvant-induced arthritis) animal test models. The compounds have high LD₅₀ and high therapeutic index, and appreciable analgesic and antipyretic activity.

5-SUBSTITUTED tetrazoles are metabolically stable, acidic functions having comparable acidity as that of corresponding carboxylic acids^{1,2}. Several workers have reported retention^{3,4} or improvement⁵ or even abolition⁶ of biological activity of various carboxylic acids on replacement of carboxyl function by 5-tetrazolyl group. Juby *et al.*^{7,8} reported both retention and diminution of anti-inflammatory activity among series of tetrazole analogues of N-phenylanthranilic acids and indole-3-acetic acids among which intrazole, a tetrazole analogue of indole-3-acetic acid, was claimed⁹ to have lower level of toxicity over the available anti-inflammatory agents. We, therefore, undertook the synthesis of tetrazole analogues of already reported¹⁰ anti-inflammatory indan-1-acetic acids (I) with a view to get a more potent and less toxic anti-inflammatory agent.

In the present communication we report the synthesis of the title compounds (IV) starting from the corresponding indan-1-acetic acids (I) via the intermediate amides (II) and nitriles (III) and the anti-inflammatory activity of IV compared to that of phenylbutazone. The detail pharmacologic evaluation of the potent compounds (compounds IVb and IVc) will follow soon.

Syntheses of the title compounds were carried out following the scheme given below.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in Gallenkamp melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. The ultraviolet and infrared spectra were recorded on Beckman spectrophotometer, Model No. 25 and Beckman Acculab 10, respectively. The spectral data of the compounds reported here gave characteristic absorption bands¹¹ of their respective functional groups and thus conformed well with their proposed structures (II-IV).

The key intermediate, indan-1-acetic acids (I), were synthesized by the general method of cyclodehydration with polyphosphoric acid of the corresponding phenylglutaric acids and subsequent reduction of the resulting indan-3-keto-1-acetic acids by the Clemmensen method as reported earlier¹².

Indan-1-acetamides (II): These compounds were prepared from the corresponding indan-1-acetic acids (I) via the acid chloride intermediate by reaction with dry ammonia. The solid amides formed were purified by crystallization from hot water.

Indan-1-acetonitriles (III): The appropriate amide (II) was finely powdered and mixed thoroughly with 10-15 times its weight of phosphorus pentoxide and then refluxed in dry benzene for 5-10 hr with occasional shaking. The resulting nitrile was extracted with chloroform, washed free from acids, and distilled under reduced pressure to get the pure nitrile (III).

5-(Indan-1'-yl)methyltetrazoles (IV): These compounds were prepared by heating a mixture of appropriate nitrile (III), ammonium chloride, activated sodium azide and 50 ml of dry dimethylformamide at 120-150° for 18-36 hr following the method of Finnegan *et al.*¹³. The resulting tetrazole (IV) was separated by extracting with aqueous potassium

* Author for correspondence.

TABLE 1—PHYSICO-CHEMICAL DATA OF 5-(INDAN-1'-YL)METHYLTETRAZOLES AND THEIR INTERMEDIATE AMIDES AND NITRILES

Starting material (I) m.p. °C ^p	Intermediate amides ^q (II)		Intermediate nitriles ^q (III)		R.I./°C	Tetrazoles ^q (IV)	
	Yield (%)	m.p. °C	Yield (%)	b.p. (°C/mm Hg)		Yield (%)	m.p. °C
a: X=Y=H/55-56	95-98	97-98	88	130/2.5	1.5420/25	65	114-115
X=OCH ₃ , Y=H/97-98	94-95	110-111	75-78	155/1.0	1.5432/25	75	147-148
c: X=Y=OCH ₃ /159.5-161	88-90	169-170	68-72	195/0.8	1.5470/28	59	181-182

p Melting points of the starting materials were taken from the reference 12.

q Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen analyses of all the compounds were within $\pm 0.3\%$ of theory.

TABLE 2—ANTI-INFLAMMATORY ACTIVITY OF 5-(INDAN-1'-YL)METHYLTETRAZOLES IN COMPARISON TO PHENYLBUTAZONE (Values are average of 6 animals per dose)

Compound No.	Dose (mg/kg) (oral)	Percent increase in paw volumes (mean \pm SE)			
		2 hr	3 hr	4 hr	23 hr
IVa	100	70.4 \pm 3.32 ^d (19.00) ^f	82.0 \pm 3.64 ^b (24.35)	94.8 \pm 4.21 ^c (22.04)	59.8 \pm 2.53 (12.06)
IVb	100	52.6 \pm 3.77 ^b (39.47)	68.2 \pm 3.08 ^a (37.08)	79.6 \pm 3.63 ^a (34.54)	52.6 \pm 2.68 ^d (22.65)
	50	59.4 \pm 3.41 ^b (31.64)	76.8 \pm 4.12 ^b (29.15)	87.5 \pm 2.87 ^a (28.04)	56.7 \pm 2.60 ^e (16.62)
IVc	100	43.8 \pm 3.36 ^a (49.60)	63.4 \pm 2.95 ^a (41.51)	79.0 \pm 2.64 ^a (35.03)	54.8 \pm 2.29 ^d (19.41)
	50	52.6 \pm 3.84 ^b (39.47)	72.3 \pm 4.29 ^b (33.30)	88.6 \pm 3.52 ^b (27.14)	58.4 \pm 2.71 (14.12)
Phenylbutazone	100	48.5 \pm 2.75 ^a (44.19)	61.7 \pm 3.31 ^a (43.08)	75.3 \pm 2.58 ^a (38.07)	54.1 \pm 2.32 ^d (20.44)
	50	58.7 \pm 3.28 ^b (32.45)	73.2 \pm 2.38 ^a (32.47)	84.6 \pm 3.30 ^a (30.43)	57.4 \pm 2.98 ^e (15.59)
Saline (Control)	—	86.9 \pm 3.48	108.4 \pm 4.13	121.6 \pm 3.82	68.0 \pm 2.81

^{a-e} Probability values (calculated as compared to control using Student's *t*-test): a < 0.001, b < 0.005, c < 0.01, d < 0.025, e < 0.05.

^f Figures in parentheses represent percent inhibition of foot edema.

hydroxide solution and was finally purified by crystallization from hot water.

The physico-chemical data of 5-(indan-1'-yl)methyltetrazoles and their intermediate amides and nitriles are summarized in Table 1.

Pharmacology :

The title compounds were screened for their anti-inflammatory activity in one acute (carrageenin-induced edema) and one chronic (adjuvant-induced arthritis) animal test model.

Carrageenin-induced rat paw edema method : The method was essentially that of Winter *et al.*¹⁴. Male albino rats weighing 120-130 g were divided at random into groups of 6 animals each and each group received orally either the test agent (dissolved in aqueous sodium hydroxide at pH 7.5 \pm 0.2) or saline, 1 hr before intradermal injection of carrageenin (Marine Colloids, Inc., U.S.A.) (0.1 ml of 1.0% solution in 0.9% saline) into the plantar surface of the right hind paw of each rat. The paw volumes upto a fixed mark at the level of lateral malleolus were measured before and after 2, 3, 4 and 23 hr of carrageenin administration with a simple advice as reported earlier¹⁵. The average percent increase in

paw volume of each group was calculated and compared against that of the control group (saline) taking phenylbutazone as standard. The results are given in Table 2.

Adjuvant-induced arthritis in rats : Following the method of Newbould¹⁶, male albino rats weighing 160 \pm 10 g were divided at random into groups of 6 animals each. Each group received orally either the test agent (dissolved in aqueous sodium hydroxide at pH 7.5 \pm 0.2) or saline, once daily for 14 days starting from the day before the administration of 0.05 ml of Freund's complete adjuvant (Difco, U.S.A.) into the plantar surface of right hind paw of each rat. Both the hind paw volumes upto a fixed mark at the level of lateral malleolus were measured before and daily after adjuvant administration. Results were expressed as the percent increase in paw volumes above the initial volume and then compared against that of the saline treated control group. The formation of nodules and appearance of erythema in tail, nose and ears were observed and graded arbitrarily as mild, moderate and severe for comparison. Change in body weight of the animals during the test period was also recorded for comparison (Table 3).

TABLE 3—INHIBITORY EFFECTS OF TWO 5-(INDAN-1'-YL)METHYLTETRAZOLES COMPARED TO THAT OF PHENYLBUTAZONE ON ADJUVANT-INDUCED ARTHRITIS IN RATS

(Values are average of 6 animals per dose)

Compound No.	Daily oral dose mg/kg	Percent increase in hind paw volumes (mean \pm SE)			Uninjected 13th Day	Degree of sec. lesion	Mean body weight change g/100 g
		3rd Day	Injected 8th Day	13th Day			
IVa	100	84.2 \pm 3.56 ^c (20.11) ^f	59.6 \pm 3.24 ^b (27.84)	64.1 \pm 2.88 ^a (34.12)	29.3 \pm 2.63 ^d (32.64)	Mod.	+5.8
IVb	100	72.8 \pm 2.94 ^b (30.98)	46.6 \pm 3.06 ^a (43.58)	46.2 \pm 3.18 ^a (52.52)	19.3 \pm 2.76 ^b (55.63)	Mild	+10.5
	50	81.0 \pm 2.75 ^b (28.15)	54.2 \pm 2.94 ^b (34.38)	55.7 \pm 2.57 ^a (42.75)	25.8 \pm 3.12 ^c (40.69)	Mod.	+6.1
IVc	100	74.2 \pm 3.86 ^b (29.60)	52.0 \pm 2.46 ^a (37.04)	53.9 \pm 2.78 ^a (44.60)	25.4 \pm 3.09 ^c (41.61)	Mod.	+7.8
	50	82.6 \pm 4.24 ^d (31.68)	58.5 \pm 3.10 ^b (29.18)	62.3 \pm 3.53 ^a (35.97)	29.6 \pm 2.85 ^d (31.95)	Mod.	+6.5
Phenylbutazone	100	76.6 \pm 4.18 ^b (27.32)	49.2 \pm 3.43 ^a (40.44)	48.0 \pm 3.60 ^a (50.67)	23.5 \pm 2.77 ^b (45.98)	Mod.	+9.4
	50	83.8 \pm 3.45 ^c (20.49)	55.5 \pm 2.86 ^b (32.81)	59.7 \pm 3.28 ^a (38.64)	29.8 \pm 3.30 ^a (31.49)	Mod.	+6.8
Saline (Control)	—	105.4 \pm 3.82	82.6 \pm 3.35	97.3 \pm 3.62	43.5 \pm 3.05	Severe	+3.5

^{a-e} Probability values (calculated as compared to control using Student's *t*-test), a < 0.001, b < 0.005, c < 0.01, d < 0.025, e < 0.05.

^f Figures in parentheses represent percent inhibition of foot edema.

Results and Discussion

From the results of carrageenin-edema test (Table 2), it is seen that 5-(6'-methoxy-indan-1'-yl)methyltetrazole (IVb) and 5-(5', 6'-dimethoxy-indan-1'-yl)methyltetrazole (IVc) are significantly more potent than 5-(indan-1'-yl)methyltetrazole (IVa) and that the potency of the former two compounds remain close to that of phenylbutazone. Though IVc shows higher potency initially its duration of action is shorter than that of IVb.

Adjuvant-induced arthritis test in rats shows a biphasic response. The initial response starts immediately after adjuvant administration and reaches a maximum on the 3rd day and the final phase starts from the 9th day and continues till the end of the experiment (13th day). Results of this test (Table 3) show that all the test agents significantly inhibit both the phases of edema formation as well as the development of secondary lesion at the dose levels used. Adjuvant-induced arthritis test results give further support to the earlier findings of carrageenin-induced edema test that both IVb and IVc possess almost the same degree of anti-inflammatory potency. Further scrutiny of the results, however, reveal the peculiar feature that IVc possesses higher initial potency whereas IVb retains activity for longer duration. Consequently, IVb has emerged as a more active compound than IVc in chronic adjuvant-induced arthritis test. This peculiarity of IVc may be due to the inherent intrinsic property of the molecule which apparently has better transport facilities leading to a rapid absorption and elimination of the compound.

It is clear from these results that like analogous indan-1-acetic acids (I)¹⁰, methoxy substitution in the indan ring moiety of these compounds (IV) improves activity, which may be due to their enhanced

lipophilic character imparted by such substitution and that these tetrazole derivatives have a quicker onset but shorter duration of action compared to the previously reported¹⁰ analogous indan-1-acetic acids. Thus, these tetrazole analogs of indan-1-acetic acids (I) retain significant activity of the latter.

Preliminary studies on the more potent tetrazole derivatives (compounds IVb and IVc) also reveal that they are significantly more potent than phenylbutazone in their analgesic and antipyretic activity and they are much less ulcerogenic as well as less toxic (oral LD₅₀ in mice, >1000 mg/kg) than the latter. These findings warrant their detail pharmacological evaluation and work in this direction is in progress.

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References

1. F. R. BENSON in "Heterocyclic Compounds", (Ed.) R. C. ELDERFIELD, John Wiley and Sons, Inc., New York, 1967 p. 8.
2. R. A. SCHERRER in "Anti-inflammatory Agents", (Eds.) R. A. SCHERRER and M. W. WHITEHOUSE, Academic Press, New York, 1974, Vol. 13-I, p. 54.
3. J. M. MCMANUS and R. M. HERBST, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1959, 24, 1464.
4. J. K. ELWOOD, R. M. HERBST and G. L. KILGOUR, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1965, 240, 2073.
5. G. F. HOLLAND and J. N. PEREIRA, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1967, 10, 149.

6. B. BROUWER-VAN STRATTEN, D. SOLINGER, C. VAN DE WESTERINCH and H. VELDSTRA, *Rec. Trav. Chim.*, 1958, **77**, 1129.
7. P. F. JUBY, T. W. HUDYMA and M. BROWN, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1968, **11**, 111.
8. P. F. JUBY and T. W. HUDYMA, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1969, **12**, 396.
9. J. S. FLEMING, M. E. BIERWAGEN, J. A. L. CAMPBELL and S. P. KING, *Arch. Int. Pharmacodyn. Ther.*, 1969, **178**, 423.
10. A. ROY, J. K. GUPTA and S. C. LAHIRI, *Indian J. Physiol. Pharmacol.*, 1980, **24**, 810.
11. C. N. R. RAO in "Chemical Applications of Infrared Spectroscopy", Academic Press, New York, 1963, p. 258.
12. S. C. LAHIRI and J. K. GUPTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 1041.
13. W. G. FINNEGAN, R. A. HENRY and R. LOFQUIST, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 3908.
14. C. A. WINTER, E. A. RISLEY and G. W. NUSS, *Proc. Soc. Exp. Biol. Med.*, 1962, **111**, 544.
15. A. ROY, S. M. ROY, J. K. GUPTA and S. C. LAHIRI, *Indian J. Physiol. Pharmacol.*, 1980, **24**, 369.
16. B. B. NEWBOULD, *Brit. J. Pharmacol. Chemother.*, 1963, **21**, 127.